

Observations on the Tomato Jellyfish *Crambione mastigophora* (Maas, 1903) of the Philippines

In

Integrating molecular and morphological evidence revives the blubber jellyfish, *Catostylus purpurus* (Scyphozoa: Rhizostomeae; Catostylidae) of the Indo-Pacific (Philippines)

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Summary

We report on the observation of the tomato jellyfish *Crambione mastigophora* (Maas, 1903) and its bloom near Corong Corong beach, El Nido, Palawan in April 2020. Notably, the gastrovascular canal system of this species exhibits dome-shaped intracircular anastomoses that do not connect to their radial canals. Additionally, this material was used as comparative reference for the genus *Catostylus*, providing new insights into the morphology and biology of these jellyfish. Our findings contribute to the understanding of the diversity and ecology of jellyfish in the Philippines.

Supplementary Fig. 1. Medusae and bloom of the tomato jellyfish *Crambione mastigophora* Maas, 1903 observed *in situ* on April 2020 near Corong Corong beach (11°10'05.2"N, 119°23'30.5"E) in El Nido, Palawan. (A) Aggregates of the tomato jellyfish, (B) mature medusa *in situ*, (C) arrangement of gastrovascular canal system (broken lines for emphasis) of this live tomato jellyfish with dome-shaped intracircular anastomoses that do not connect to their radial canals; a lappet = arrow.